

Validity of The Principle of Additivity of Viscosity B Coefficients in The Mixtures of Weak Acids and Their Salts

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The principle of additivity of viscosity B (and A) coefficients has been extended to mixtures of weak acids and salts. On this basis, equations giving the degree of dissociation (α) of the weak acid solutions have been developed in terms of various A and B coefficients. The α calculated from viscosity measurements is compared with the values obtained from the direct pH measurements on weak acid solutions.

It is well established that the viscosity B coefficients of Jones-Dole's equation are additive in the sense that the B coefficient differences between pairs of salts, having common anions, are constant in dilute solutions and independent of the nature of the anion¹ (cf. Kohlrausch's law of independent migration of ions). An attempt has been made in the present study to extend such additivity principle to a mixture of components each of which is characterised by a specific B coefficient. The particular systems investigated are of the general type, weak acid+salt combinations, and we have proposed equations, by way of invoking such "extended" additivity, that lead to the evaluation of an important property of weak acid solutions, namely the degree of dissociation, α , from viscosity measurements. The latter, thus obtained, is compared with the value of α derived from direct pH measurements carried on such acid solutions. A satisfactory agreement between these values of α will be taken to justify the extension of the above additivity to mixtures. The following equations are derived for acetic acid, but should equally apply to any combination of weak acid and the corresponding salt.

Theory and working formulae: Let α be the degree of dissociation of acetic acid solution at a concentration C mol. litre⁻¹ and at a given temperature.

Assuming additivity of the viscosity B coefficients at concentration C, one may write,

$$C B_{\text{obs}} = C (1-\alpha) B_{\text{ACOH}} + \alpha C B_{\text{H}^+} + \alpha C B_{\text{ACO}^-}$$

where B_{ACOH} is the B coefficient of acetic acid "molecule" i.e., the undissociated acetic acid and B_{obs} the observed B coefficient at concentration C.

Therefore, $B_{\text{obs}} = (1-\alpha) B_{\text{ACOH}} + \alpha B_{\text{ACO}^-} \dots (1)$, B_{ACO^-} being the B coefficient of the "fully dissociated" acetic acid.

By analogy, the viscosity A coefficient (Grüneisen effect), as observed in the above acetic acid

solution, is given as,

$$A_{\text{obs}} = (1-\alpha) A_{\text{ACOH}} + \alpha A_{\text{ACO}^-} \dots (2)$$

It is interesting to note from eqs. (1) and (2) that at infinite dilution $\alpha = 1.0$ and therefore $B_{\text{obs}} = B_{\text{ACO}^-}$ and $A_{\text{obs}} = A_{\text{ACO}^-}$, which one would expect. Hence, eqs. (1) and (2) are consistent.

By rearrangement of eq. (1), we obtain

$$\alpha = \frac{B_{\text{obs}} - B_{\text{ACOH}}}{B_{\text{ACO}^-} - B_{\text{ACOH}}} \dots (3)$$

so that α , the degree of dissociation at a concentration C, can be derived from the measured viscosity B coefficient of acetic acid solution, B_{obs} , at the same concentration provided that the B coefficients of the "fully dissociated" acetic acid (B_{ACO^-}) and the undissociated acid (B_{ACOH}) are known.

For the general case of weak acid, HA, and its salt eq. (3) reads,

$$\alpha = \frac{B_{\text{obs}} - B_{\text{HA}}}{B_{\text{H}^+\text{A}^-} - B_{\text{HA}}} \dots (3a)$$

B_{ACO^-} is calculated by adding up B_{H^+} and B_{ACO^-} ; the latter are derived from viscosity studies on solutions of strong acids and acetates.

B_{ACOH} is obtained through an approximation. On the assumption that acetic acid is undissociated in presence of a dilute solution of an acetate, B_{ACOH} will be given by the difference between the viscosity B coefficient of a mixture of acetate and acetic acid, (B), an experimental quantity, and that of the acetate. Such a method is based on an extension of the principle of additivity of B coefficients (and A coefficients) to a mixture as mentioned above.

For the purpose, viscosity measurements are conducted on a number of mixtures of sodium acetate (at a given concentration, say 0.1M) and different stoichiometric concentrations of acetic acid (say, 0.05M, 0.075M, 0.1M and 0.15M). With the above mentioned supposition that acetic acid at these concentrations is fully undissociated

in presence of 0.1M sodium acetate, one would obtain from the Jones-Dole's equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + (A) \sqrt{C} + (B) C + \dots \quad (4)$$

in which (A) and (B) are composite quantities, given by

$$(A) = A_{\text{ACOH}} + A_{\text{NaOAc}} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

and

$$(B) = B_{\text{ACOH}} + B_{\text{NaOAc}} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

while η and η_0 are the viscosity coefficients at the same temperature of the mixture of acetate and acetic acid, having a mean (molar) concentration C, and of water, respectively.

On obtaining (A) and (B) from the intercept and slope respectively of the graphical plot of

$$\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1\right) / \sqrt{C} \text{ vs } \sqrt{C} \text{ [vide. eq.(4)], } A_{\text{ACOH}} \text{ and } B_{\text{ACOH}}$$

are derived, using eqs. (5) and (6) and with a knowledge of A_{NaOAc} and B_{NaOAc} from independent experiments on acetate solutions.

To calculate α according to eq.(3) one requires a knowledge of B_{obs} as well. The Jones-Dole's equation, as applied to an acetic acid solution at a stoichiometric concentration C, reads,

$$B_{\text{obs}} C + A_{\text{obs}} \sqrt{C} = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where B_{obs} and A_{obs} are given by eqs. (1) and (2).

On substituting A_{obs} from eq. (2) in eq. (7) one obtains

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 = B_{\text{obs}} C + \left[(1 - \alpha) A_{\text{ACOH}} + \alpha A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+} \right] \sqrt{C}$$

which, on rearrangement, becomes

$$B_{\text{obs}} = \frac{\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1\right)}{C} - \frac{1}{C^{3/2}} [C A_{\text{ACOH}} - C\alpha A_{\text{ACOH}} + C\alpha A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+}] \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Remembering that $C\alpha = C_{\text{H}^+}$, the hydrogen ion concentration of the solution, it follows,

$$B_{\text{obs}} = \left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right] - \frac{1}{C^{3/2}} [C A_{\text{ACOH}} + C_{\text{H}^+} (A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+} - A_{\text{ACOH}})] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Thus, B_{obs} is obtained from eq. (9) with a knowledge of A_{ACOH} and $A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+}$ ($A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+}$ is given as $A_{\text{NaOAc}} + A_{\text{HCl}} - A_{\text{NaCl}}$), and pH (i.e., C_{H^+}) of the given solution of acetic acid.

Eq. (9) may be rewritten as

$$B_{\text{obs}} C^{3/2} = \sqrt{C} \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right) - [C A_{\text{ACOH}} + C_{\text{H}^+} (A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+} - A_{\text{ACOH}})] \quad (10)$$

On inspection of eq. (10) it is clear that at infinite dilution ($C=0$, $C_{\text{H}^+}=C\alpha=0$), $\alpha=1.0$ and $\eta=\eta_0$.

On such substitution in eq. (10), both sides of the latter vanish. Hence eq. (10) is also consistent.

On substituting the values of B_{ACOH} , $B_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+}$ and B_{obs} , determined as described above, in eq. (3) α is calculated and then the value is compared with the one obtained by direct pH and hence C_{H^+} ($=C\alpha$) measurement of the given acetic acid solution.

Materials : An Ubbelohde type (three necked) all-glass viscometer was used for the determination of viscosities. The flow time was recorded by means of a stop watch reading up to 0.1 of a second. The average (of at least four observations) flow time for water through the capillary of the viscometer was 502.6 sec. The temperature of study was maintained at $30.0 \pm 0.05^\circ$ by the use of a water-thermostat provided with a solid state relay unit and an electrical contact thermometer.

The chemicals used, namely glacial acetic acid, propionic acid, hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate were of AnalaR grade (B.D.H. and E. Merck) while sodium propionate was prepared from the acid and anhydrous sodium carbonate (AnalaR), followed by crystallisation (twice) from water.

The solutions were prepared in deionised water of conductivity less than 3μ mho.cm⁻¹. An electrical balance, reading upto 10 μ g, was used for recording weights in the preparation of solutions and measurements of density (by using a specific gravity bottle).

Experimental

(i) The viscosity B coefficients of sodium acetate and sodium propionate were determined by noting the time of flow at a number of concentrations, ranging from 0.05M to 0.5M, of each of these solutions as well as that of water, all at 30°, and then having recourse to the graphical plot [viz. eq. (4)] in each case. The viscosity A coefficients of these compounds were also noted from the intercepts of the plots.

(ii) A series of mixtures, which were 0.1M with respect to NaOAc and successively 0.05M, 0.075M, 0.1M and 0.15M with respect to acetic acid, were prepared and the composite constants (A) and (B) [vide. eqs. (5) and (6)] were determined in the same manner as above (acetic acid was considered fully undissociated in these mixtures).

(iii) From (i) and (ii), A_{ACOH} and B_{ACOH} for the undissociated acetic acid were derived.

(iv) The steps (ii) and (iii) were repeated for propionic acid and sodium propionate.

(v) A and B for hydrochloric acid were determined as in (i) above by studying viscosity of its solutions. Next, by using the measured A_{NaOAc} from (i) and noting A_{NaCl} from the literature² $A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+}$ was calculated from the relation,

$$A_{\text{ACO}^- \text{H}^+} = A_{\text{NaOAc}} + A_{\text{HCl}} - A_{\text{NaCl}}$$

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY DATA FOR SOLUTIONS

Temperature=30°
Viscosity of water (η_0) at 30°=0.7975 cp
Density of water (ρ_0) at 30°=0.9956 g cm⁻³

Solution	Molar concentration/ M C	\sqrt{C}	Coefficient of viscosity of solution/cp η	$\eta Sp/\sqrt{C}$ ($\eta Sp = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1$)	B coefficient (Slope of linear plot of $\eta Sp/\sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C})
Sodium acetate	0.1	0.3162	0.8131	0.0620	
	0.2	0.4472	0.8303	0.0920	
	0.3	0.5477	0.8494	0.1190	0.180
	0.4	0.6324	0.8670	0.1380	(B ₁)
	0.5	0.7071	0.8877	0.1600	
Sodium propionate	0.1	0.3162	0.8284	0.1230	
	0.2	0.4472	0.8613	0.1790	
	0.25	0.5000	0.8776	0.2010	0.384
	0.30	0.5477	0.8957	0.2250	(B ₁)
	0.40	0.6324	0.9311	0.2650	
Hydrochloric acid	0.2	0.4472	0.8042	0.0190	
	0.4	0.6324	0.8146	0.0340	
	0.6	0.7745	0.8228	0.0410	0.063
	0.8	0.8944	0.8338	0.0510	(not used elsewhere)
	1.0	1.0000	0.8416	0.0560	
	Mean molar concentration				
Sodium acetate (0.1M) + Acetic acid (undissociated)	0.0650 0.0750 0.1000 0.1250	0.2549 0.2738 0.3162 0.3535	0.8215 0.8258 0.8316 0.8381	0.1180 0.1295 0.1353 0.1437	Composite B coefficient (B) 0.285
Sodium propionate (0.1M) + Propionic acid (undissociated)	0.0625 0.0750 0.1000 0.1250	0.2500 0.2738 0.3162 0.3535	0.8298 0.8345 0.8458 0.8563	0.1620 0.1700 0.1920 0.2090	Composite B coefficient (B) 0.488

$A_{H^+A^-}$ for propionic acid was also calculated in the same manner.

(vi) B_{AcO-H^+} was obtained as $(B_{H^+} + B_{NaOAc} - B_{Na^+})$ in which B_{H^+} and B_{Na^+} were the literature values¹ while B_{NaOAc} was the measured value from (i). B for fully dissociated propionic acid was obtained in the same way.

(vii) B_{obs} was next determined by measuring the viscosity as well as the pH of a 0.1M acetic acid solution (and of 0.1M propionic acid) and then using eq. (9) in which the values of A_{ACOH} and A_{ACO-H^+} , as obtained above, were used.

(viii) The degree of dissociation α was finally calculated, by using eq. (3) from the values of B_{obs} , B_{ACOH} and B_{ACO-H^+} . The α so obtained was compared with the value derived from the measured pH of 0.1M acid solution.

Results and Discussion

A Synopsis of results has been given in Tables, 1 to 6, covering the determination of various A and B coefficients as well as the hydrogen ion concentration of the solutions and finally, the degree of dissociation (α) of the weak acid solutions studied (Table 6). The corresponding α obtained from the direct pH measurements (say, α_{pH}) is also included for the sake of comparison in the same Table.

The degree of dissociation for both acetic and propionic acids, as obtained from the present viscosity studies, is seen from Table 6 (5th column) to

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY MEASUREMENTS ON SALT SOLUTIONS AND STRONG ACID, HCl

Solution	B coefficient B ₁	A coefficient A ₁
Sodium acetate	0.180	0.012
Sodium propionate	0.384	0.008
Hydrochloric acid	0.063	0.005
	(not used elsewhere)	

TABLE 3—VISCOSITY AND pH MEASUREMENTS ON WEAK ACID SOLUTIONS

Solution	$(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1)/C$	pH	$C_{H^+} = 10^{-pH}/g \text{ ion. litre}^{-1}$
Acetic acid (0.1M)	0.2031	2.80	0.03158
Propionic acid (0.1M)	0.2270	2.96	0.00110

TABLE 4—VISCOSITY MEASUREMENTS ON MIXTURES OF WEAK ACIDS AND SALTS

Solution	Composite B coefficient (B)	Composite A coefficient (A)	* B coefficient of undissociated acid $B_{HA} = (B) - B_1$	** A coefficient of undissociated acid $A_{HA} = (A) - A_1$
Acetic acid + Sodium acetate	0.285	0.043	0.105	0.031
Propionic acid + Sodium propionate	0.488	0.046	0.103	0.038

* $B_1 \equiv B_{NaA}$; ** $A_1 \equiv A_{NaA}$.

TABLE 5—DATA TAKEN FROM LITERATURE^{1,2}

Solution/Ion	B coefficient	A coefficient
H ₃ O ⁺	0.0709 ²	—
Na ⁺	0.0859 ²	—
NaCl	0.0793 ¹	0.0062 ¹

able satisfaction that the kind of agreement in α values, as elaborated in the preceding paragraph, well justifies the extension of additivity principle of viscosity B (and, A) coefficients to mixtures of the type investigated in the present case.

TABLE 6—DERIVED QUANTITIES

Solution	B coefficient of fully dissociated acid $B_{H^+A^-} = B_{NaA} + B_{H_3O^+} - B_{Na^+}$	A coefficient of fully dissociated acid $A_{H^+A^-} = A_{NaA} + A_{HCl} - A_{NaCl}$	$B_{obs} = \left[\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right) / C \right]$ $-\frac{1}{C^{3/2}} [CA_{HA} - C_{H^+} (A_{H^+A^-} - A_{HA})]$	$\alpha = \frac{B_{obs} - B_{HA}}{B_{H^+A^-} - B_{HA}}$	αpH
Acetic acid (0.1M)	0.165	0.0107	0.106	0.020	0.0158
Propionic acid (0.1M)	0.369	0.0067	0.108	0.017	0.0110

be of the same order of magnitude as the values (αpH) calculated from the pH of the weak acid solutions (6th column of Table 6). Furthermore, the relative strengths of these acids also turn out in the right order i.e., acetic > propionic from these viscosity experiments. The percent error in α in both the cases is about the same and in the same direction (error positive).

Taking into view the approximate nature of the treatment as well as the simplifying assumptions introduced at a number of steps to obtain the various A and B coefficients, it can be said with reason-

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